

Elements Of Successful Sustainable Development In The Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 01, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Political Elements, Socio-Economic Elements, Security Elements, Sustainable Development, Iraq.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7606406</p>	<p><i>Achieving sustainable development at an upward pace according to well-thought-out plans and in a parallel direction between all target areas requires many political, economic, social and security elements in Saudi society in order to establish a new development situation not previously familiar with the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the premise that there is a set of social, economic, security. This study used several approaches to address and familiarize with all aspects related to the topic such as the historical method and the descriptive approach. The study concluded that the promotion of sustainable development in Saudi Arabia to advanced degrees was behind which the basic elements represented by political, social, economic and security elements, and that these elements affect in terms of availability and quality on the extent of the state's achievement in the field of achieving sustainable development. The study also recommended the development of comprehensive plans and innovative solutions that help integrate economic, social and environmental aspects provide reliable data to rely on in continuous evaluations, encourage evaluations to promote "good governance", make the government make optimal use of resources a priority, and institutionalize the evaluation process.</i></p>

Introduction

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is at the forefront of the countries of the Arab region, which has been able to move at a balanced pace on the path of sustainable development and improve the economic, social, political and environmental reality, based on a set of elements that represented the mainstay of sustainable development, foremost of which are social, economic, security and political elements. After 2015, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia sought to make major political, economic, social and administrative transformations that are unfamiliar to the Saudi scene at an accelerated pace for the purpose of seeking to diversify sources of income, development in the field of energy, eradicate poverty, improve the standard of living of the Saudi citizen, promote social development and eliminate the global stereotype on social rights, especially therefore, the study will examine what are the political, economic, social and security elements that enabled the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to move towards sustainable development, what are those policies it has adopted, the extent to which difficulties can stand in the way of achieving its goal in sustainable development and how much they have been achieved or are just slogans such as slogans that are considered a prominent landmark in developing countries.

Research importance

The importance of research lies in presenting and evaluating the political, economic, social and security elements that encouraged the Kingdom to move towards sustainable development and the policies, plans and strategies selected for a sustainable development process adopted by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the targeted areas and the reasons for selecting those policies and plans, as well as knowing the possibility and ability of the Kingdom to transform into a leading development model in the Arab region in the near future as a result of those policies, and presenting the effectiveness of those policies followed and the most important obstacles that may stand in the way of achieving the desired goals and what methods it has adopted to overcome these obstacles.

Research problem

The problem of research is that achieving sustainable development at an upward pace according to well-thought-out plans and in a parallel direction between all target areas requires many political, economic, social and security elements in Saudi society because these elements establish a new situation in development that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has not previously been familiar with. The question arises, has the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia succeeded.

1. What are the social and economic elements of sustainable development in Saudi Arabia?
2. How did Saudi Arabia's security elements contribute to sustainable development?
3. What are the political elements of sustainable development in Saudi Arabia?
4. How much did these diverse elements contribute to Saudi Arabia's success in reaching real

development after 2015?

Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis of the study is based on the fact that there are a set of social, economic, security and political elements that enabled the kingdom of Saudi Arabia to develop solid development policies that contributed to creating and achieving a desirable public situation and developing and modernizing at all levels, including political, social, economic and environmental, within what is known as the Saudi Vision 2030 initiative.

Research methodology

In order to verify the hypothesis of the study, the methodology of scientific research required resorting to several curricula, each of which was employed in its place within the context of the study. The historical method was relied upon to show the most prominent historical aspects related to the history of development in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study also relied on the descriptive analysis method to adapt the available information with the know-how plan and its scientific goal, by analyzing the foundations and dimensions of the elements of sustainable development in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia in its political, economic, social and security fields.

First requirement: the social and economic elements of development in Saudi Arabia

Saudi society, like other societies, is affected by many rapid and successive social changes that are related to the nature of the conditions of society and the historical nature it is going through. The youth group is the most affected in these changes. Due to the importance of the role played by socio-educational, cultural and academic institutions in social development, the government of the kingdom of Saudi Arabia has paid great attention to society, especially the youth and the process of building their personality properly reflects positively on the whole society. This was confirmed by successive development plans in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which aimed at developing the capabilities of the Saudi person, achieving his ambitions, meeting his aspirations and improving the standard of living. These plans also stressed the importance of the human element and improving it in all areas. ⁽¹⁾

Development in the field of education

To this day, education is one of the most important criteria used in determining the level of development in contemporary societies. Since the establishment of the kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the government has played a great role in securing free education and expanding it vertically and consensually, until it became part of the broader social equality project, believing in the principle of equal opportunities. The interest in education was what distinguished education in Saudi Arabia in the period of the sixties and seventies was that it was not limited to a particular class, region or family, but education became a legitimate right for all. ⁽²⁾ In the second millennium, the proportion of the Saudi and non-Saudi population enrolled in the study increased, as shown in figure (1).

Figure (1): the percentage of those enrolled in education in Saudi Arabia for the year 2000

The population of the kingdom of Saudi Arabia reached in the middle of 2000 (20.846.884). The enrollment rate in education is one of the most important social variables that affect and are affected by other demographic and economic influences. According to a study conducted in (1421 ah / 2000 ad) that the population aged 6-30 years (64.5%) are enrolled in education and the Saudis. ⁽³⁾ The education policy in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia was characterized by the education of women by allocating schools for them to prevent their mixing with males, and employing audiovisual communication techniques in teaching methods to achieve this privacy, which did not prevent women from achieving their educational gains and reaching advanced stages in higher education, and focusing on the educational curricula that prepare the Saudi girl to become a mother of abroad in the field of arts, humanities and social sciences is still high compared to the rest of the scientific disciplines, in 2019 the number of scholarships in humanities and social disciplines reached (11.263) students. ⁽⁴⁾ Since the launch of the 'Custodian of the Two Holy Mosques' initiative for external scholarship in 2005, this program was scheduled to continue for five years until 2010, but its success in its first five-year plan prompted the Ministry of Higher

education to extend the program for a second period of five years ending in 2015 and then a recently issued third period with the approval of the custodian of the two holy mosques to extend it for five years ending in 2020. The number of scholarships has reached more than eighty years after the establishment of the kingdom of Saudi Arabia and more than a decade after the launch of the custodian of the two holy mosques program, about 150 thousand scholarships distributed over more than thirty countries in the finest international universities and in all scientific, medical, engineering and practical disciplines required by the labor market and major development projects have graduated from this program about (55,000 students with a stumbling rate not exceeding (2%), according to statistics contained on the website of the Saudi Ministry of Higher Education. These large numbers of scholarships are explained by the figures allocated by the kingdom in its recent budgets.⁽⁵⁾ The Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has sought to develop education and transform it from the quantitative to the qualitative side and improve its quality at all educational stages. It has taken care of the problem of illiteracy and combating it with different methods and strategies. The literacy rate in the kingdom has decreased to (5.6%) as a result of the use of different methods in education and the shift from the concept of narrow literacy to the concept of continuous education and the sustainability of education, literacy of literacy, informatics and technical illiteracy and the modification of the tasks of the general administration of adult education (formerly) to the general directorate of continuing education, which targets adults who have not enrolled in education, to provide them with the skills necessary to erase their illiteracy and promote the values of lifelong learning. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has supervised (2,259) schools whose service benefits more than (90) thousand students, and has worked to increase the centers of the educated neighborhood (305) centers with a total number of beneficiaries (114,939) students. These centers aim to empower women in the age group (15-50) years that hold a high school certificate to gain the necessary professional skills that prepare those.⁽⁶⁾

Energy development

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia ranks first in the production of crude oil among the Arab oil exporting countries, where it produces more than (10.145) million barrels per day. It is the largest producer of oil in the world and has a prominent role in stabilizing the world oil markets. It is natural that oil and gas play an essential role in developing the industrial base of economic sectors, as oil products are used for local consumption, in addition to being a raw material for many industries. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has also taken an economic and social path to promote production capacity. Industrial production has increased, the agricultural base has expanded and the educational and health situation has improved. The strategic choice of the kingdom has become industrialization and diversification of sources of income.⁽⁷⁾ Saudi Arabia has the largest oil reserves in the world estimated at about 264.2 billion barrels, and oil exports represent (90%) of total export revenues, about (75%) of government budget revenues and (45%) of GDP. According to the Ministry of Commerce and Industry in 2012, the kingdom's oil reserves are estimated at (55%) of the reserves of the Gulf Cooperation Council countries and (29%) such as industry, agriculture and mining.⁽⁸⁾ Over the past decades, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has relied on oil revenues as a major source of national income. The development witnessed by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the past was due to high oil prices. Oil prices were the ones that guide development in the Saudi economy. Therefore, the main goal of the ten development plans from 1970-2019 was to reduce dependence on oil as a major source of income, that is, in the sense of "economic diversification" and to encourage sustainable development that is not affected by the change in oil prices. The private sector in most developed and developing countries plays a major role in growth and economic diversification. In the case of Saudi Arabia, the government owns major companies such as "Aramco Oil Company" and owns a large share in companies such as the Saudi Basic Industries Corporation and the Saudi Electricity Company, in addition to more than (70%) of most banks and companies operating in the Saudi financial market.⁽⁹⁾ Saudi Arabia played a key role in the global oil market, accounting for almost (16%) of proven global reserves, as it had an effective impact on stabilizing the economy and growth in the world. Its production rose to achieve a balance between supply and demand in the oil market, for example, during the first Gulf War 1990-1991, the 2003 Gulf War, Hurricane Katrina in 2005, and the Libyan crisis 2010-2011, the kingdom's production increased to meet the demand for oil and the supply decreased from other sources.⁽¹⁰⁾ The rise in oil prices since 2000, specifically after 2003, has reduced the direct financial pressure driving economic reform. With oil prices reaching (\$55) per barrel of crude in 2004 against the lowest price of (\$10) per barrel in 1998, the Saudi government had sufficient resources to avoid structural reforms, and real GDP increased by (7.2%) in 2003, according to an IMF report in 2005.⁽¹¹⁾ The private sector in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is characterized by the fact that Saudi investors are committed to investing in their countries, although there are huge funds abroad that are easy to transfer outside the kingdom. This is what distinguishes the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from the rest of the countries outside the Gulf Cooperation Council and sometimes some GCC countries to some extent and many oil exporting countries. This advantage results from a lack of confidence in equal competition opportunities in the international investment environment on the one hand, and a sense of confidence and confidence towards respect for property rights within the kingdom on the other. Lack of confidence in the external investment environment existed before the attacks of September 11, 2001. U.S.-Saudi relations have deteriorated, with Saudi investors refusing to

act as entrepreneurs in major industrial cities, which is why few saudi companies have been established in the united states or in europe.⁽¹²⁾

Development in industry and agriculture

In the field of agriculture since the thirties of the twentieth century, abdul-aziz al saud has brought agricultural engineers from the united states of america (us) and asked them to submit reports to him to assess the agricultural situation in the country. These experts began to tour the kingdom in all directions, determine its resources and estimate its productive efficiency. After a while, they submitted to the king a 100-page report, new sources of information, development of available sources and recruitment of experts to benefit from groundwater and expansion of cultivated areas.⁽¹³⁾ there have been positive transformations in the field of agriculture since the fifties of the twentieth century, many farmers have been interested in the use of manure, prolonging early and late planting seasons, addressing the problem of soil salinity, building irrigation and puncture networks in agricultural areas and developing animal products, especially after the dahraan air base agreement (1951) with us.⁽¹⁴⁾ and (the fourth point project) signed with the us in 1951,⁽¹⁵⁾ to improve crops and types of pastures and livestock and training on the exploitation of desert and agricultural resources in the kingdom.⁽¹⁶⁾ in the field of industry, the kingdom of saudi arabia has worked to create a modern industry, aimed at diversifying the production base, reducing dependence on oil and exporting it, and increasing the contribution of the industrial sector to the process of sustainable development and developing the national workforce, to develop a solid industrial and technical base. The saudi government was aware that the oil resources it depends on in implementing its development projects and programs are subject to factors and influences beyond its control, such as supply and demand and fluctuations in global markets. Oil is one of the most important depleted resources that do not renew, so it had to find an ideal alternative to accelerate the achievement of development based on diversifying the economic base and raising the level of productivity of the saudi economy. In light of the developments of globalization and technological development, successive development plans have stressed the importance of industrialization as the ideal alternative to accelerate the achievement of development goals. The growth rate in the industrial sector of the kingdom of saudi arabia has increased, doubling the number of factories produced during the past decades from (358) factories in 1973 to (5177) factories in 2012. The capital of these factories increased from 220 billion saudi riyals to more than (523) billion saudi riyals in 2014.⁽¹⁷⁾ the kingdom of saudi arabia has been able to attract new qualitative industries. The number of new quality factories reached (12) of them local high quality, international american and korean and factory in malaysian partnership, confirming the kingdom's role in shaping the future of the industrial sector. The saudi authority for industrial estates was formed one of the most important elements of the national economy and its industrial arm. The introduction with high quality, one of the most prominent customers of the factory is saudi aramco, and most of the materials used in the industry are products of saudi sabic, as well as the korean (foamtech) factory in jeddah with an area exceeding 14,000 square meters and investments exceeding 95 million riyals (25) million dollars. The factory produces the material (steel foam) used in million dollars, and the saudi commission is working to develop and manage industrial cities with sustainable growth and an economic environment with national expertise and high logistical capabilities.⁽¹⁸⁾ the kingdom of saudi arabia has the highest potential of solar energy resources in the world, solar geographic information systems (solar) data confirms the availability of horizontal radiation capabilities (chi) of (2,425) kwh / h / m², and this puts the kingdom at the forefront of countries compared to the countries of the european union and the middle east and north africa, in the field of with other countries, as well as the kingdom has one of the largest wind electricity performance indicators in the gcc region, where the average wind speed in the kingdom reaches from (4,10) to (5,10) m/s, so the kingdom has high wind energy capabilities in the coastal areas of the arabian gulf, the red sea and the gulf of aqaba, which are priority sources that must be included in the renewable energy master plan in the kingdom.⁽¹⁹⁾ the basic law of governance in the kingdom of saudi arabia has approved basic principles for the preservation of the state's resources, wealth and funds as public rights that must be harnessed to serve the public and used for their benefit. Article (14) of the basic law confirmed the state's ownership of all wealth deposited in the ground or outwardly, and that the use, protection and regulation, article (73) of the statute also prohibited the payment of money from the public treasury except in accordance with the provisions of the budget, and if the budget items do not expand, it must be by royal decree. Article (74) also prohibited the sale, lease or disposal of state property except as determined by the law. Articles (76), (77) and (78) also regulate the general budget of the state, and decided on the means of verifying the aspects of exchange by preparing the final account.⁽²⁰⁾ the construction sector constitutes a large share in the economy of the kingdom of saudi arabia. The sector achieved high rates over many years, recording (5.6%) in 2015 as a result of the increase in spending by the private and public sectors. Despite the decline in oil prices and the decrease in government expenditures in 2016, which led to the delay in the implementation and cancellation of many projects and the contraction of the construction sector by (1.9%) during the first quarter of 2016 to settle at (31.4) billion saudi riyals. However, the huge investments over the past five years amounted to more than 1 trillion saudi riyals, which are currently under implementation. The huge investments made by government and non-governmental institutions between 2010-2015 led to an

annual growth rate of (6.9%) in the construction sector, and the sector's contribution to gdp increased to (5.04%) in 2015.⁽²¹⁾

The second requirement: security elements in the kingdom of saudi arabia

Security has an importance in the life of human beings and groups. With regard to individual security, man cannot practice his usual work except by achieving security. Security is a vital and conditional requirement to achieve every sound humanitarian action. The importance of collective security is also concentrated in what the world monitors in its state, groups and even its members of funds, power and the different number to defend security guarded. There is no country that has a public security department and a full body concerned with this issue. Security management has evolved to include many divisions necessitated by the nature of the competence of the present era. Security sciences have become a branch of humanities, which are taught in security institutes and colleges. It means that no nation can live without security and no society can rise without it.⁽²²⁾ article (33) of the saudi basic law obliges the state to establish and equip the armed forces in order to protect and defend the faith, the two holy mosques, society and the homeland, which is a mutual duty between the homeland and the citizen. Article (36) and the state have the responsibility to provide security for citizens and residents on its territory, and prevented the restriction of the actions of anyone or arrest him unless he does what is required. Article (37) also imposed on housing to prevent their entry without the permission of their owners and prevent their inspection except as determined by the regulations. Since one of the most important factors of consolidating security, preserving rights and spreading reassurance is the imposition of penalties for encroachment and aggression, article (38) affirmed the imposition of sanctions on committing prohibitions as a deterrent and reprimand, but not exceeding the punitive function so that the punishment is limited to the perpetrator and does not exceed others, and that the punishment is only for committing what is prohibited by law or regulation, and emphasizing the guarantee of security for telegraphic and postal correspondence, telephone intelligence and other means of communication.⁽²³⁾ since 2004, armed attacks in the kingdom of saudi arabia have decreased significantly, so the kingdom has been able to build its capabilities with regard to combating terrorism and extremist ideologies. For example, during the first months of 2008, the security forces of the saudi ministry of interior arrested (701) militants who were believed to be planning to attack oil fields on other sites. The saudi government announced that (991) people were terrorism in july 2008; the ministry of interior issued a statement urging citizens to remain vigilant against extremist activities even within their families, and the need to report any suspicious behavior.⁽²⁴⁾ the saudi government is making efforts to combat the dissemination of terrorist ideas through the internet, which is used by al-qaeda in the arabian peninsula to promote terrorist ideas. In 2003-2004, the competent authorities followed up and closed suspicious websites and arrested those in charge of them. The ministry of islamic affairs carried out a large media campaign to educate saudi youth about the correct teachings of the islamic religion in an effort to prevent the youth segment from slipping into the methods of terrorism. This campaign took several means, including friday sermons in mosques and placing articles on the internet. In 2007, the government issued special identity cards to mosque imams and religious guides to prevent unauthorized people from delivering friday sermons or other religious sermons, and this continued. In 2008, the government established rehabilitation programs for people with extremist ideas, to reintegrate them into saudi society and emphasize that these people are victims of extremism that leads them through films and videos urging them to sympathize with the islamic peoples of afghanistan and iraq.⁽²⁵⁾ the large expansion of digital transformation processes and the high rates of cyberattacks and data breach risks have made the kingdom of saudi arabia more keen to provide a secure environment for information and data through a solid security system. A royal order was issued in 2017 to form the national cyber security authority, whose main task is to develop, implement and supervise strategies in a balanced manner between security and confidence to achieve a safe and reliable saudi cyberspace that contributes to growth and prosperity, and in order to reduce cyber risks to information internally and externally. The competencies of the national cyber security authority also included developing national encryption policies and standards, following up on compliance and updating them and providing the required degree of protection for data and systems. National networks for civil and commercial purposes based on best practices and global standards.⁽²⁶⁾ the kingdom of saudi arabia has achieved a remarkable achievement in the field of cybersecurity, ranking second in the world out of 193 countries and first in the arab world, the middle east and the continent of asia according to (the global cybersecurity index). The us topped the list with 100 degrees and the kingdom came with the united kingdom in second place with (99.54) degrees each. The global cybersecurity index is issued by the united nations agency specialized in information and communications technology. The kingdom of saudi arabia jumped eleven places from 2018 in the new classification (global cybersecurity index) since the launch of vision 2030, where it was ranked (46). Globally, in the 2017 edition of the index, the cybersecurity index is measured according to a set of elements, including the existence of cybersecurity strategies and policies, the extent to which national plans and standards are implemented on the ground, the availability of the training and qualification process for cadres in the field of cybersecurity and the efforts and initiatives made in this regard, and the existence of a legislative and legal structure that supports cybersecurity.⁽²⁷⁾ the kingdom of saudi arabia has moved towards strengthening the security aspect and working to increase arms purchases. The kingdom ranked fourth in the world according to

the ranking of the most spending countries on arms purchases in 2013, after it was ranked seventh between 2011-2012, and its need to increase the efficiency of the security services to protect the regime and regional factors represented by Saudi-Iranian tensions regarding the situation in Syria and Saudi) the US government also allowed the sale of long-range air-to-surface missiles in 2013, the first deal of its kind with a country in the region, and recently became the kingdom's possibility of obtaining nuclear weapons in cooperation with the state of Pakistan, whose nuclear program has long received Saudi support and support since the 1990s.⁽²⁸⁾ International indicators concerned with security also showed the progress of the kingdom of Saudi Arabia and is issued by the G20 countries. The kingdom ranked first among the G20 countries, ahead of the five permanent members of the UN Security Council in the (presence of the population feeling safe while walking alone at night index) for 2020, surpassing China, Canada and among the G20 countries over China and 2019 is ahead of the five permanent members of the UN Security Council, ahead of France and the US and second place for the same index among the G20 countries, and the kingdom ranked third among the G20 countries after Australia and Japan, ahead of Canada, South Korea, France and Germany in the 2019 Security Index.⁽²⁹⁾

The third requirement: political elements (good governance) in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia

The kingdom of Saudi Arabia has achieved successes at the international and local levels in the field of anti-corruption and unlimited support (for the control and anti-corruption commission) (Nazaha). Vision 2030 stressed the importance that the Saudi leadership attaches to the issue of combating corruption and enhancing transparency as a method of the state. The kingdom works to eliminate financial and administrative corruption and achieve transparency to combat corruption and strengthen international cooperation in the field of combating corruption, and the Riyadh Initiative.⁽³⁰⁾ aimed at enhancing informal international cooperation between the concerned authorities to combat corruption, employing information technologies to enhance integrity in the public sector and issuing the first ministerial statement to represent a future road map that highlights a number of issues such as asset recovery, beneficiary transparency, denial of safe haven and foreign bribery.⁽³¹⁾

Good governance is the best way to achieve high-quality services, guarantee human rights and apply the principles of justice among members of society, to ensure high levels of economic and human development in the long term. Governance provides an administrative method based on the participation of beneficiaries of services in drawing strategies and implementing control of the administrative process to provide more effective services at the local and state levels in general.⁽³²⁾ The term (governance) is one of the most important terms circulating in the development field since the end of the eighties, where it was first used by (the World Bank) in 1989, which considered governance "the method of exercising power in managing the economic and social resources of the country for development." The World Bank's use of the concept of government came as an affirmation that the development crisis in many developing countries is essentially a governance crisis due to the corruption of some political systems and poor planning and follow-up.⁽³³⁾ According to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), good governance is participatory, fair, transparent, accountable and efficient use of resources and based on the rules of justice, equity and the rule of law. Good governance is based on fighting corruption, nepotism, bureaucracy and mismanagement, so governance is an effective mechanism for exercising transparency and accountability.⁽³⁴⁾ In the field of combating corruption in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the competent authorities are the control and auditing authority, the general directorate of administrative investigations and other government and administrative bodies. The national anti-corruption commission was established in 2011, which aims to protect public money, fight corruption and protect integrity in the work of the agencies under its jurisdiction, namely public institutions in the state and companies laws aimed at strengthening the fight against corruption and money laundering, such as the banking supervision system issued in 2005, the application of the electronic system in daily transactions to reduce friction between citizens and state employees, and support scientific research and administrative development in the fight against corruption.⁽³⁵⁾ Among the measures adopted by the kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the fight against corruption is to encourage the cooperation of citizens in protecting integrity and combating corruption, encouraging those who have information related to the practice of corruption to go to the concerned authorities, and providing a 24-hour hotline managed by the directorate general of investigations (administrative investigations) to receive reports from citizens about these practices. The one million riyals) about (47) million US dollars, and the kingdom has also witnessed a major shift in the application of e-government transactions, where many government sectors provide their services electronically. The Saudi Arabian Monetary Agency was established in 2004 and services program (SADAD) through which service fees and fines are paid. The application of electronic transactions plays a prominent role in reducing the incidence of corruption and providing an accurate system for accounting and auditing without human intervention.⁽³⁶⁾ At the international level, cooperation with all countries of the world and international organizations specialized in the field of combating corruption was emphasized, accession to the United Nations Convention Against Corruption of 2003, which entered into force in 2013, in addition to the previous measures taken by the kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the field of combating corruption, the royal palace issued the formation of a higher anti-corruption committee in 2017, as a result, (381) people were summoned, most of them were arrested, their money was confiscated, and they were prevented from traveling. The work of this committee

continued until 2019, and ended its work by recovering (106) billion us dollars after completing all investigations.⁽³⁷⁾ as a result of all previous measures taken by the kingdom of saudi arabia and the steps of reform in all fields within vision 2030, the kingdom of saudi arabia jumped to 57th place in the list of the best countries in the world in the corruption perceptions index issued by transparency international.⁽³⁸⁾ the kingdom of saudi arabia advanced five full positions according to the report issued by the organization on the corruption perceptions index for 2017, and the kingdom ranked (62) in the 2016 report, and the kingdom of saudi arabia also advanced one position at the level of arab countries compared to the previous report. The corruption perceptions index is a composite indicator published by transparency international. Some behaviors linked to corruption such as bribery and nepotism are measured. Embezzlement of public money and abuse of power for personal interests, and some data also measure anti-corruption mechanisms such as accountability mechanisms for corrupt officials and the ability of the government to apply mechanisms to promote integrity.⁽³⁸⁾ in 2019, the kingdom of saudi arabia advanced seven international positions in the ranking (corruption perceptions index) issued by transparency international, where the kingdom achieved 51st place globally out of 180 countries, and advanced in its position among the economic group of twenty (g20)⁽⁴⁰⁾ to achieve tenth place. This index issued by transparency international on an annual basis is based on perceptions of the spread of corruption in countries through a set of extrapolations and evaluations on corruption collected through data sources from international organizations accredited to transparency international. The kingdom of saudi arabia is currently witnessing a road map to combat corruption that constitutes a basic basis for the vision. Kingdom 2030 aims to carry out reforms and reduce the risk of corruption and emphasize the position of the kingdom of saudi arabia among the 20 most economically powerful countries in the world.

Conclusion

The study found that the promotion of sustainable development in saudi arabia to advanced levels was behind which the basic elements represented by political, social, economic and security elements, the most important of which are: human resources, increasing infrastructure expenditures, natural resources, technology, and the role of governments in providing appropriate institutional, economic and political infrastructure and achieving partnership with the private sector and all segments of society to achieve the goals of sustainable development. These elements affect in terms of their availability and quality over the extent of the country's achievement in the field of achieving sustainable development. saudi arabia launched vision 2030 in order to define a roadmap for the country towards a prosperous future in all areas of development, based on three pillars: a vibrant society, a thriving economy, and an ambitious homeland. With the aim of reducing dependence on oil, diversifying and strengthening the economy and thus improving well-being for the public. achieving the ambitious and comprehensive sustainable development goals as well as achieving the goals of vision 2030 will require several actions, including the development of comprehensive plans and innovative solutions that help integrate economic, social and environmental aspects, in addition to adopting real programs to encourage the private sector and civil society institutions to engage in development programs. As well as the existence of mechanisms to measure the impact of development programs, with the need to conduct adequate studies of strategic and development projects before their implementation, provide reliable data to rely on in ongoing evaluations, encourage evaluations to promote good governance, continuous development of the capacity of assessors. The government should prioritize the optimal use of resources. Institutionalize the evaluation process.

Reference

- Qasim mustafa mohammed, alghanim ghanem bin saad, the role of civil society organizations in achieving social development for saudi youth in light of the kingdom's vision 2030, journal of studies in social work, volume 1, issue 47, 2019.
- Muhammad bin sunitan, saudi political and tribe, the arab network for research and publishing, beirut, 2008, 1st edition, p. 78.
- Saudi ministry of economy and planning, department of public reforms and information, population characteristics in saudi arabia, 2000. See www.state.gov.sa, (accessed 21/1/2022).
- Muhammad ibn sanitan, *ibid*, p.75.
- Asharq al-awsat newspaper, custodian of the two holy mosques scholarship program, 2014. See www.aawsat.com (accessed 23/3/2022).
- Hussein mashaikhi, kingdom's efforts in literacy and continuing education, naded al- arab newspaper, 2019, see www.nbdalarab.com, (accessed 2/4/2022)
- Naji sari faris, the economic effects of oil policy in the kingdom of saudi arabia, center for basra and arabian gulf studies, journal of gulf economy, no. 29, 2016, p. 189.
- Abdul karim bin khalaf al-huwaish, industrial sector in saudi arabia, economic, analytical and spatial perspective, university of sharjah journal, volume 12, no. 1, 2015, p. 219.
- Ahmed adnan al-tayt, anis al-omari, post-oil era in saudi arabia: the ration for economic diversification, journal of the islamic university for economic and administrative studies, volume 26, no. 3, 2018, p. 26.

- Malika pant, alberto bihar, saudi arabia addressing emerging economic challenges to sustain growth, international monetary fund, 2015, p.13.
- Monica malik, tim neiluk, saudi arabia in the balance, center for arab unity studies, beirut, lebanon, 2013, 2nd edition, p. 111.
- Giacomo luciani, saudi arabia in libra, center for arab unity studies, beirut lebanon, 2013, 2nd edition, p. 196.
- Sabri faleh al-hamdi, the modernization movement in saudi arabia 1926-1953, arab house of science publishers, lebanon, beirut, 2014, 1, p. 57.
- In the last years of world war ii, the us tried to acquire an air base at dhahran airport in saudi arabia, to facilitate military operations in the war with japan, and immediately after the end of the war, the saudi government agreed to conclude an agreement to build a us military air base in dhahran. See: ayhan jaafar mohammed taher, dhahran rule agreement between the us and saudi arabia in 1951, journal of arts, literature, humanities and sociology, no. 63, 2021.
- The fourth point program is a us technical assistance program dedicated to developing countries, especially asia, africa and latin america. The program was first announced in the speech of us president harry truman on january 20, 1949 on the occasion of his assumption of the presidency for a second term. The speech talked about the four objectives of us foreign policy. The program was approved by the us congress on june 5, 1950 and allocated 25 million us dollars for fiscal year 1950/51. A committee was formed in the us under the name of the technical assistance group. See: muhammad fouad muhammad, the united states of america towards saudi arabia: from the end of world war ii until the death of king abdulaziz bin saud 1945-1953, master's thesis, faculty of arts, ain shams university, cairo, 1992, p. 14
- Sabri faleh al-hamdi, *ibid*, p.68.
- Abdul karim khalaf al-huwaish, *ibid*, p. 220.
- Bandar muslim, saudi arabia attracts new quality industries, ashraq al-awsat newspaper, no. 15601, 2021, see www.aawsat.com, (accessed 5/2/2022).
- Riyadh economic forum, towards sustainable economic development a study in the economics of alternative and renewable energy in the kingdom of saudi arabia challenges and prospects for the future, session 7, 2018, p. 57.
- Muhammad bin abdullah al-marzouqi, authority in the kingdom of saudi arabia, research and publishing, beirut, 2014, 1st edition, p. 157.
- Sherihan al-manzlawi, overview of the saudi economy, national commercial bank economic department, 2016, see www.alahli.com, (accessed 10/2/2022).
- Abdullah bin abdul hassan al-turki, intellectual security and the care of the kingdom of saudi arabia, lecture delivered at the public security training city in mecca, 2001, p. 2.
- Muhammad bin abdullah al-marzouqi, *ibid*, p. 159.
- Ruel major, kingdom of arabia in the balance, political economy, society and foreign affairs, center for arab unity studies, beirut, lebanon, 2nd edition, 2013, p. 357.
- Ruel major, *ibid*, p. 358.
- The unified national platform, cybersecurity in the kingdom, see www.my.gov.sa, (accessed on 5/2/2022).
- Abdul halim hafina, how saudi arabia achieved cybersecurity achievement globally, sky news arabia, 2021, see www.skynewsarabia.com. (accessed 4/2/2022).
- Kawthar abbas al-rubaie, firas abbas hashim, saudi arabia regional status transitions, journal of political science research, faculty of political science – mustansiriyah university, no. 31-32, 2016, p. 6.
- Ashraq al-awsat newspaper , the safest saudi newspaper among the g20 countries, 2020, see www.aawsat.com, (accessed 5/2/2022).
- It is an initiative that establishes a global platform linking anti-corruption agencies to exchange information around the world and promotes joint international engagement among the competent authorities in the g20 countries. See: the saudi press agency, the united nations adopts the riyadh global initiative to enhance the efforts of the international community in combating corruption, see <https://www.spa.gov.sa/2313680>, (accessed 12/17/2021)
- Al-arab international economic newspaper, kingdom achieves international and local successes in the field of combating corruption, 2021, see www.aleqt.com, (accessed 23/2/2022).
- Al-bassam bassam abdullah, good governance saudi arabia case study, academy for social and humanities studies, volume 6, no. 1, see www.asjp.cerist.dz (accessed 23/3/2022).
- Nael moussa rabaia, governance and its applications in public universities – saudi arabia as a conceptual model of governance, comprehensive electronic journal of scientific and educational research, no. 15, 2019, p. 6.
- Nael musa rabaiba, *ibid*, p. 7.
- Mohammed hassan saeed, means of international law to combat corruption crimes, a thesis submitted to complete the requirements for obtaining a master's degree, faculty of law middle east university, jordan, 2019, p. 150.
- Ahmed bin mohammed al-salem, brief overview of saudi arabia's efforts in the field of protecting integrity and

combating corruption, al-riyadh newspaper, no. 15470, 2021, see www.alryiadh.com, (accessed 1/2/2022).
Mohamed hassan saeed, *ibid*, p. 151.

It is an international non-governmental organization founded in 1993 with its headquarters in berlin, germany, whose goal is to address corruption, including political corruption. The organization publishes an annual index of corruption managers in the world. See www.m.mareffa.org, (accessed 24/2/2022).

Saudi press agency, kingdom leads five places in corruption perceptions index according to transparency international index, riyadh, 2018, see www.spa.gov.sa, (accessed 19/2/2022).

An international conglomerate was established in the late twentieth century in the german city of berlin, to face financial crises that threaten global economic and financial stability. The group includes in addition to the european union 19 countries, namely argentina, australia, brazil, canada, china, france, germany, india, indonesia, italy, japan, mexico, russia, saudi arabia, south africa, turkey, south see www.amp-dw.com, (accessed 13/1/2022).

Al-arab international economic newspaper, saudi arabia advances seven places in the corruption perceptions index in 2019, 2019, see www.aleqt.com, (accessed date 29/1/2022)

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